

Testing Equality of Principal Eigenvectors of Spiked Covariance Matrices

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Abstract—The problem of detecting differences between the principal eigenvectors of the covariance matrices of two independent multivariate time series is studied. A statistical test is proposed which, under certain separability conditions, consistently converges to a quantity that measures the distance between the two principal subspaces of the true covariance matrices. By assuming a spiked covariance matrix model, a central limit theorem is established that characterizes the asymptotic behavior of the binary hypothesis test in high-dimensional settings. This result enables the specification of the asymptotic false alarm probability of the test and facilitates the analysis of its power under the alternative hypothesis. The study is conducted within a random matrix theory (RMT) framework, where both the sample size and the observation dimension grow proportionally. The findings provide deeper insights into how high-dimensional effects influence the reliability and performance of the test.

Index Terms—Eigenvector test, random matrix theory, binary hypothesis test, principal components, spiked covariance matrix.

I. INTRODUCTION

The principal eigenvector of a covariance matrix indicates the direction in which the data varies the most, capturing the most significant pattern in a dataset. Among other multiple applications, it can be used to identify statistical changes in the observations and to detect significant deviations in data over time. By comparing this vector across different time intervals, one may detect alterations in the underlying statistical pattern of the data, making this approach effective in applications like remote sensing, fault detection or financial anomaly detection. This has motivated a number of studies of the properties of the eigenvectors of the sample covariance matrix in the statistical literature [1]–[3]. A lot of interest has been given to the binary hypothesis problem consisting in deciding whether the principal subspace of the observed covariance matrix coincides with a certain pre-specified value, a problem for which a variety of tests has been provided [4]–[6].

Conventional analysis of the problem has been carried out from the asymptotic perspective, assuming that the sample size is much larger than the observation dimension. However, recent interest has shifted towards more general asymptotic regimes in which the observation dimension is allowed to scale up with the sample size. This falls under random

matrix theory (RMT) approaches, which help understand the challenges of limited sample sizes by analyzing cases where the ratio of samples to dimensions stays constant, even as both grow without bound. A particularly interesting model that is suitable in multiple applications is the spiked sample covariance matrix model, which essentially assumes that a few eigenvalues (spikes) are singled out from the rest of the spectrum (bulk). Under some separability conditions, a phase transition occurs [7] that allows to separate the contribution of the spikes from the bulk of the spectrum in the asymptotic empirical eigenvalue distribution. Most of the literature on spiked covariance matrices assumes a model where the bulk is generated by a single eigenvalue with increasing multiplicity, so that the empirical eigenvalue distribution converges to a Marchenko-Pastur law [8]–[10]. More recent studies have extended this framework to cases where the bulk of the spectrum accepts a more general description [11], [12]. Herein, we consider sample covariance models under this more general setting.

Our main objective is to study the problem associated with testing whether the principal eigenvectors of the covariance matrices of two independently observed multivariate series coincide. To the best of our knowledge, the literature has focused so far on testing whether the principal subspace of the sample covariance matrix differs from a pre-established template. To that effect, multiple characterizations of the asymptotic behavior of the sample eigenvectors have been published in the literature, especially under the above introduced spiked covariance model, see e.g. [13]–[19]. The present contribution differs from these previous studies in a number of aspects. First, our test will be based on the comparison of two statistically independent time series in order to determine whether the principal eigenvector associated to their covariance matrices coincides. Second, we focus on the general case where the bulk eigenvectors of the true covariance matrix can be multiple and are allowed to fluctuate within certain limits. Third, we consider a consistent estimator of the covariance subspaces introduced in [20] instead of the conventional plug-in sample estimates. This will allow us to derive a statistic that, under the subspace equality hypothesis, fluctuates around a value that is independent of the actual principal eigenvectors.

II. STATISTICAL MODEL OF THE OBSERVATIONS

Consider two statistically independent multivariate processes $\mathbf{y}_j(n)$, $j \in \{1, 2\}$. Assume that a total of N_j obser-

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variations are available for the j th time series and let \mathbf{Y}_j denote an $M \times N_j$ matrix containing these observations, that is

$$\mathbf{Y}_j = [\mathbf{y}_j(1) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{y}_j(N_j)].$$

These observations can be either real or complex valued, and we will introduce a variable $\varsigma \in \{0, 1\}$ such that $\varsigma = 1$ the observations are real valued, whereas $\varsigma = 0$ indicates they are complex circularly symmetric. The following statistical assumption will be made.

(As1): The observations $\mathbf{y}_j(k)$ are all independent and can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}_j(k) = \mathbf{R}_j^{1/2} \mathbf{x}_j(k)$$

where \mathbf{R}_j is an Hermitian positive definite matrix and $\mathbf{x}_j(k)$ is a vector of independent and identically distributed random entries with zero mean and unit variance.

The different eigenvalues of \mathbf{R}_j are denoted $0 < \gamma_1^{(j)} < \dots < \gamma_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$ ($j \in \{1, 2\}$) and have multiplicity $K_1^{(j)}, \dots, K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$, where \bar{M}_j is the total number of distinct eigenvalues. We will also denote as $\Pi_k^{(j)}$ the orthogonal projection matrix onto the subspace associated with the k th eigenvalue of \mathbf{R}_j , so that we can alternatively write this matrix as

$$\mathbf{R}_j = \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{M}_j} \gamma_k^{(j)} \Pi_k^{(j)}$$

where the rank of $\Pi_k^{(j)}$ is $K_k^{(j)}$.

Let us now consider the eigenvector(s) associated to the maximum eigenvalue of this matrix, which is assumed to have known multiplicity $K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$. The subspace associated with the maximum eigenvalue $\gamma_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$ is therefore denoted as $\Pi_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$. We are therefore interested in the binary hypothesis test problem

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : \quad & \Pi_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} = \Pi_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)} \\ H_1 : \quad & \Pi_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} \neq \Pi_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)}. \end{aligned}$$

It is well known that the similarity between the principal subspaces of two different covariance matrices $\mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2$ can be measured as

$$\eta_M = \text{tr} \left[\Pi_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} \Pi_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)} \right]. \quad (1)$$

When the two principal subspaces have dimension one, that is $K_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} = K_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)} = 1$, we can write $\Pi_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} = \mathbf{e}_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} \left(\mathbf{e}_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} \right)^H$ for a principal eigenvector $\mathbf{e}_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$, and η_M takes the form

$$\eta_M = \left| \left(\mathbf{e}_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} \right)^H \mathbf{e}_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)} \right|^2$$

which belongs to the set $\eta_M \in [0, 1]$. Clearly, $\eta_M = 1$ indicates that the two principal eigenvectors are equal, whereas $\eta_M < 1$ indicates that they do not. This implies that η_M can be used to determine whether the two principal eigenvectors of \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 coincide.

In practice, we do not have access to the true covariance matrices of the different processes, so that the quantities η_M

are generally unknown. One of the possibilities is to replace the true eigenvalues with their sample estimates, assuming that the multiplicity of the largest true eigenvalues are known. In other words, by considering the sample covariance matrices

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j = \frac{1}{N_j} \mathbf{Y}_j \mathbf{Y}_j^H$$

and letting $\tilde{\Pi}_{\bar{M}_i}^{(i)}$ denote the projection matrix onto the principal subspace of $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j$ (assuming $K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$ known), we could consider the following plug-in estimate of η_M , namely

$$\tilde{\eta}_M = \text{tr} \left[\tilde{\Pi}_{\bar{M}_1}^{(1)} \tilde{\Pi}_{\bar{M}_2}^{(2)} \right]. \quad (2)$$

This estimator is obviously consistent when $N_1, N_2 \rightarrow \infty$ for a fixed M . However, it is well known to be strongly biased in finite sample size scenarios where N_i, M are comparable in magnitude. To specifically tackle this situation, we will consider here the asymptotic regime whereby the three quantities M, N_1, N_2 are all large but comparable in magnitude. This is further specified in the following assumption:

(As2): The sample sizes N_j are a function of the observation dimension M , that is $N_j = N_j(M)$. Furthermore, when $M \rightarrow \infty$ we have $N_j(M) \rightarrow \infty$ in a way that $M/N_j \rightarrow c_j$ for some constant $0 < c_j < \infty$, $j \in \{1, 2\}$.

Now, observe that we are considering a scenario where the true covariance matrices \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 are allowed to vary for each value of M . This means that their eigenvalues and eigenvectors are also allowed to fluctuate, although with some limitations as specified in the following:

(As3): All the eigenvalues, eigenvectors and associated multiplicities of \mathbf{R}_j may vary with M but we always have $\inf_M \gamma_1^{(j)} > 0$ and $\sup_M \gamma_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} < \infty$. Furthermore, the multiplicity of the largest eigenvalue is assumed known and bounded, i.e. $\limsup_{M \rightarrow \infty} K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} < \infty$.

Now, it is well known [21] that the plug-in estimator in (2) is not consistent under **(As1)**-**(As3)**. Fortunately, there exists an alternative estimator that, under some specific assumptions, is consistent in the large dimensional regime [20]. To introduce this estimator, let us denote by $\hat{\lambda}_k^{(j)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_k^{(j)}$ the eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors of the sample covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j$, where $\hat{\lambda}_1^{(j)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{\lambda}_M^{(j)}$. Consider the matrix

$$\hat{\Pi}_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} = \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{M}_j} \hat{\alpha}_k^{(j)} \hat{\mathbf{e}}_k^{(j)} \left(\hat{\mathbf{e}}_k^{(j)} \right)^H \quad (3)$$

where

$$\hat{\alpha}_k^{(j)} = - \sum_{r=M-K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}+1}^{\bar{M}_j} \left(\frac{\hat{\lambda}_r^{(j)}}{\hat{\lambda}_k^{(j)} - \hat{\lambda}_r^{(j)}} - \frac{\hat{\mu}_r^{(j)}}{\hat{\lambda}_k^{(j)} - \hat{\mu}_r^{(j)}} \right)$$

for $k = 1, \dots, M - K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}$, whereas for $k = M - K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)} + 1, \dots, \bar{M}_j$ we define

$$\hat{\alpha}_k^{(j)} = 1 + \sum_{r=1}^{M-K_{\bar{M}_j}^{(j)}} \left(\frac{\hat{\lambda}_r^{(j)}}{\hat{\lambda}_k^{(j)} - \hat{\lambda}_r^{(j)}} - \frac{\hat{\mu}_r^{(j)}}{\hat{\lambda}_k^{(j)} - \hat{\mu}_r^{(j)}} \right).$$

In the above expressions, we have introduced the quantities $\hat{\mu}_k^{(i)}$, $k = 1, \dots, M$, which are the solutions to the following polynomial equation

$$1 = \frac{1}{N_j} \sum_{r=1}^M \frac{\hat{\lambda}_r^{(i)}}{\hat{\lambda}_r^{(i)} - \hat{\mu}}$$

plus $[N_i - M]^+$ zeros in the undersampled regime ($N_j < M$, where we take $0/0$ to mean 0). With these definitions, we can now define the following estimator of η_M , namely

$$\hat{\eta}_M = \text{tr} \left[\hat{\Pi}_{M_i}^{(i)} \hat{\Pi}_{M_j}^{(j)} \right].$$

It was established in [20] that, under some eigenvalue separability conditions (phase transition) that will be presented next, the above estimator is consistent. To introduce this separability assumption, we need some additional definitions. Consider the following polynomial equation

$$1 = \frac{1}{N_j} \sum_{r=1}^{\bar{M}_j-1} K_r^{(j)} \left(\frac{\gamma_r^{(j)}}{\gamma_r^{(j)} - \theta} \right)^2.$$

Let $\theta_M^{(j)}$ denote the three largest solution to the above equation for any fixed M . We will assume that

(As4) For $j \in \{1, 2\}$, we have

$$\sup_M \theta_M^{(j)} < \inf_M \gamma_{M_j}^{(j)}.$$

The above assumption essentially establishes that one can always asymptotically separate the contribution from the largest eigenvalue in the asymptotic support of the empirical eigenvalue distribution. It can be shown that this condition can be always guaranteed when N_j/M is sufficiently large (i.e., when enough samples per observation dimension are available).

It follows directly from [20] that under **(As1)-(As4)** the above estimator is a consistent estimator of η_M . We therefore propose to use this statistic in order to test whether the two eigenvectors of \mathbf{R}_1 , \mathbf{R}_2 are equal, that is

$$\hat{\eta}_M \stackrel{H_1}{\lesssim} \phi \stackrel{H_0}{\gtrsim}$$

for a certain threshold $\phi \in (0, 1)$. The main objective of this paper is to analyze the performance above test and to provide a method to fix this threshold in order to specify a certain probability of false alarm under H_0 .

III. A CENTRAL LIMIT THEOREM ON $\hat{\eta}_M$

In this section we establish that the proposed consistent estimator converges to the true η_M with an error that decays as $O_p(M^{-1/2})$. We will also see that the estimator asymptotically behaves as a Gaussian random variable with zero mean and a covariance that can be expressed in closed form. An additional assumption will be needed:

(As5) The observations are Gaussian distributed and

$$\inf_M \text{tr} \left[\Pi_{M_1}^{(1)} \Pi_{M_2}^{(2)} \right] > 0.$$

According to **(As5)**, the principal eigenvectors of \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 should not be asymptotically orthogonal. This special case would require a separate analysis since the corresponding convergence rate is essentially modified.

In order to introduce the asymptotic variance, we need some additional definitions. For each M and $j \in \{1, 2\}$, we define $\Upsilon_j^{(k)}$ as

$$\Upsilon_j^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N_j} \sum_{r=1}^{\bar{M}_j-1} \frac{K_m^{(j)} \left(\gamma_m^{(j)} \right)^2}{\left(\gamma_m^{(j)} - \gamma_{M_j}^{(j)} \right)^k}$$

and we simply write $\Upsilon_j = \Upsilon_j^{(2)}$. Based on these two quantities, we define the asymptotic variance as

$$\Sigma_M = \Sigma_M^{(1)} + \Sigma_M^{(2)} + \Sigma_M^{(12)} \quad (4)$$

where, for $j \in \{1, 2\}$, we have defined

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_M^{(1)} &= \frac{2(1+\varsigma)M\gamma_{M_1}^{(1)}}{N_1(1-\Upsilon_1)} \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{M}_1-1} \frac{\gamma_k^{(1)} \text{tr} \left[\Pi_k^{(1)} \Pi_{M_2}^{(2)} \Pi_{M_1}^{(1)} \Pi_{M_2}^{(2)} \right]}{\left(\gamma_k^{(1)} - \gamma_{M_1}^{(1)} \right)^2} \\ &+ \frac{(1+\varsigma)M \left(\gamma_{M_1}^{(1)} \right)^2}{N_1(1-\Upsilon_1)^2} \left(\Upsilon_1^{(4)} + \frac{\left(\Upsilon_1^{(3)} \right)^2}{(1-\Upsilon_1)} \right) \text{tr} \left[\left(\Pi_{M_1}^{(1)} \Pi_{M_2}^{(2)} \right)^2 \right] \end{aligned}$$

where $\Sigma_M^{(2)}$ is similarly defined by interchanging the indexes $1 \leftrightarrow 2$, and where

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_M^{(1,2)} &= \frac{2(1+\varsigma)M\gamma_{M_1}^{(1)}\gamma_{M_2}^{(2)}}{N_1N_2(1-\Upsilon_1)(1-\Upsilon_2)} \times \\ &\times \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{M}_1-1} \sum_{r=1}^{\bar{M}_2-1} \frac{\gamma_k^{(1)}\gamma_r^{(2)} \text{tr} \left[\Pi_k^{(1)} \Pi_r^{(2)} \right] \text{tr} \left[\Pi_{M_1}^{(1)} \Pi_{M_2}^{(2)} \right]}{\left(\gamma_k^{(1)} - \gamma_{M_1}^{(1)} \right)^2 \left(\gamma_r^{(2)} - \gamma_{M_2}^{(2)} \right)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

We now have all the ingredients to present the main result of this work, which is formulated next.

Theorem 1: Under **(As1)-(As5)**, we have

$$M^{1/2} \Sigma_M^{-1/2} (\hat{\eta}_M - \eta_M) \rightarrow \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

where Σ_M is defined in (4).

Proof: The main idea is to express $\hat{\Pi}_{M_j}^{(j)}$ as the integral

$$\hat{\Pi}_{M_j}^{(j)} = \oint_{C_l} \frac{\hat{\omega}_j(z)}{z} \left(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j - z\mathbf{I}_M \right)^{-1} \hat{\omega}'_j(z) dz$$

where C_l is a negatively oriented contour enclosing the last $K_{M_j}^{(j)}$ eigenvalues of $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j$, where

$$\hat{\omega}_j(z) = z / (1 - N_j^{-1} \text{tr} [\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j (\hat{\mathbf{R}}_j - z\mathbf{I}_M)^{-1}])$$

and where $\hat{\omega}'_j(z)$ denotes its derivative. The main idea is then to expand the integrand following the ideas in [22] (details are omitted but can be found in [23]). ■

The above result allows to fully describe the behavior of the proposed statistic $\hat{\eta}_M$ under either one of the two considered hypotheses. In fact, it shows that the statistic will asymptotically fluctuate around η_M as a Gaussian random variable, with

a different variance depending on the underlying hypothesis. The above result can therefore be used to fix the threshold ϕ in order to specify a certain probability of false alarm under H_0 , as well as to analyze the power of the test under H_1 . In fact, there is a way of building a normalized statistic that is asymptotically pivotal (i.e. converges to a standard Gaussian). This would require a consistent estimator of the variance in (4), which can be built using RMT tools.

A very similar result could have been derived for a statistic of the type $\text{tr}(\hat{\Pi}_{M_1}^{(1)} \hat{\Pi}_{M_2}^{(2)})$, where we note that the second matrix is deterministic. The result can be proven using the same technique as the above theorem, and can be heuristically obtained by letting $N_2 \rightarrow \infty$ for a constant M in the above result. When doing so, both $\Sigma_M^{(2)}$ and $\Sigma_M^{(12)}$ converge to zero and only $\Sigma_M^{(1)}$ remains. This essentially provides some intuition on the justification of the three terms of (4): $\Sigma_M^{(1)}$ (resp. $\Sigma_M^{(2)}$) arises from the fluctuation of $\hat{\Pi}_{M_1}^{(1)}$ (resp. $\hat{\Pi}_{M_2}^{(2)}$), whereas $\Sigma_M^{(12)}$ is an additional term that arises from the interactions between $\hat{\Pi}_{M_1}^{(1)}$ and $\hat{\Pi}_{M_2}^{(2)}$.

IV. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

In order to study the accuracy of the above asymptotic description, we considered here a simulation example in which the two covariance matrices \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 are built to have $M_1 = M_2 = 4$ different eigenvalues, namely $\gamma_k^{(1)} \in \{1, 3, 5, 10\}$ and $\gamma_k^{(2)} \in \{1, 5, 8, 20\}$. In both cases, the smallest eigenvalue had multiplicity $M - 3$, whereas the other three had multiplicity one, i.e. $K_{M_j-2}^{(j)} = K_{M_j-1}^{(j)} = K_{M_j}^{(j)} = 1$ for $j \in \{1, 2\}$. The numerical study provided here focuses on the null hypothesis, which is the most interesting regime from the practical perspective. More specifically, the eigenvectors of both \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 were fixed to be the same and randomly generated from a uniform distribution in the orthogonal group. The sample covariance matrices $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_2$ were generated according to a circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution ($\zeta = 0$) with zero mean and covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 respectively.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 represent the histograms of the proposed statistic $\hat{\eta}_M$ drawn from 10^4 realizations for different sample sizes, together with the asymptotic distribution in Theorem 1 (red solid line). Fig. 1 represents the situation where $M = 20$ and Fig. 2 the case $M = 400$. In both figures, we fixed $N_1 = 6M$ whereas different values of the quotient N_2/M were considered. Observe, first of all, that under the null hypothesis the proposed statistic always fluctuates around the true value of $\eta_M = 1$, which does not depend on the structure of the covariances. This is different from the plug-in estimator in (2), which cannot be larger than $\min\{K_{M_1}^{(1)}, K_{M_2}^{(2)}\} = 1$ and will therefore fluctuate around a certain value that will depend on the structure of both covariance matrices (see [24] for details). On the other hand, the convergence in distribution towards the asymptotic Gaussian law specified in Theorem 1 can be readily checked by observing the evolution of the histograms from Fig. 1 to Fig. 2. In particular, When the observation dimension is relatively low, the error terms of order $O_p(M^{-1})$ are more noticeable. These terms can be

Fig. 1. Histogram versus asymptotic distribution of $\hat{\eta}_M$ under H_0 , where $M = 20$, $M/N_1 = 1/6$ and $M/N_2 \in \{2, 2/3, 1/3, 1/6\}$.

Fig. 2. Histogram versus asymptotic distribution of $\hat{\eta}_M$ under H_0 , where $M = 400$, $M/N_1 = 1/6$ and $M/N_2 \in \{2, 2/3, 1/3, 1/6\}$.

seen to fluctuate according to a chi-square law [16, Remark 2.7], which generate the negative skewness in the empirical distribution (cf. Fig 1).

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a binary hypothesis test in order to detect potential differences between the principal eigenvectors of covariance matrices from two independent multivariate time series. A consistent statistical test is provided that asymptotically converges to the true distance between the principal subspaces of the two covariance matrices. Assuming a spiked covariance model, we presented a central limit theorem to describe the asymptotic behavior of the binary hypothesis test in high-dimensional settings. The study is conducted within a random matrix theory framework, which provides important insights into high-dimensional effects.

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